

Exhibition review

Dinh Q Lê: on textility, weaving and unravelling

Abstract: From a life marked by disruption and displacement, Vietnamese-American artist Dinh Q Lê has crafted a distinctive aesthetic revolving around visual and metaphorical juxtapositions, using photography as his main material and conceptual resource. Born in Vietnam in 1968, he moved to the United States in the 1980s, only settling back in Vietnam in the mid-1990s. This exhibition review examines the textile quality and “textility” of his work, in Tim Ingold’s words, especially in the processes engaged in his monumental photo weavings. Inspired by mat weaving, Lê develops a new visual and semiological language by interlacing two different photographic prints cut into strips. The selection of twenty artworks exemplifies Lê’s relentless fascination for Cambodia and Vietnam’s histories of conflict, complexities and memorialization.

Keywords: Dinh Q Lê; Asian American art; textility; Vietnam; Cambodian genocide; weaving

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Dinh Q Lê, Photographing the Thread of Memory, February 8 – November 20, 2022, Musée du quai Branly – Jacques Chirac, 37 Quai Jacques Chirac, 75007 Paris, France.

From a life marked by disruption and displacement, Vietnamese-American artist Dinh Q Lê has crafted a distinctive aesthetic revolving around visual and metaphorical juxtapositions, using photography as his main material and conceptual resource. At the initiative of photography curator Christine Barthe, a retrospective of twenty of his major artworks has been on view at the Musée du quai Branly. Born in Vietnam in 1968, Lê grew up in Hâ Tien in the Mekong delta region, only a few kilometers away from Cambodia's border. From the start, his life was shaped by borderlands and crossings. About his childhood between Cambodia and Vietnam, he said: "I felt I belonged to both countries in a way. The border didn't really seem to exist, and we passed it quite easily. So many relatives and people I know live on both sides" (Morelli 2022). In 1977, when the conflict escalated between Vietnam and Cambodia, Khmer Rouge factions attacked his village. He was only nine years old and the violence he witnessed chased him ever since. Lê fled the area with his family and stayed in a refugee camp in Thailand in 1978 before migrating to Southern California a year later. Since 1996, he has returned to Vietnam and established himself in Ho Chi Minh City, where he co-founded Sàn Art, an art center supporting emerging Vietnamese artists.

In a simple, chronological scenography, the exhibition shows how, early on, Lê gained recognition for his large-scale photo-weavings mounted on fabric, using two sets of magnified silver prints cut into strips and interlaced together. From an abundance of images, he builds new visual, tactile and emotional worlds equally questioning Vietnam and Cambodia's twentieth-century histories of conflict (Choron-Baix 2009). His work gained prominence in the 1990s with pieces referring to the Vietnam War and its representations in Western photojournalism and cinema (Gardner 2015, 50-51). Lê travelled to Cambodia for the first time in 1994. His experience at Tuol Sleng Genocide Museum marked him, especially the viewing of endless rows of black and white photographs with the prisoners' faces, images to which he has constantly returned [Fig.1]. On the same trip, he also visited the Angkor temples and was struck by the paradoxical nature of Cambodian heritage (Boreth Ly 2004, 102).

What emerges in the different exhibited pieces is the inherent *textility* of Lê's practice, that is, the haptic quality engaged in his creative process to create a new language in which memory can emerge. In *The Textility of Making*, anthropologist Tim Ingold (2012, 92) details the "tactile and sensuous knowledge of line and surface that had guided practitioners through their varied and heterogeneous materials". Centered on the generative power of making, Dinh Q Lê's work embraces processes borrowed from textile crafts (Karsenty and Cutts 2022). A video of the artist in his studio shows him cutting a large photographic print into one set of strips used as the warp and another for the weft set of strips [Fig.2]. Sitting on the floor to compose his enmeshed artwork, he assembles both sets, inserting a row of weft photo strips into the ones forming the warp structure. Weaving is operated as the interlacing of two opposite temporalities, directions, and narratives to let a third one emerge.

With his recent work *Cambodia Reamker #11*, Dinh Q Lê simultaneously invokes and obfuscates the glory of the Angkorian past by showing glimpses of the Reamker's frescoes from the Royal Palace and the devastation of the Khmer Rouge genocide with haunting faces from S21. Lê does not shy away from visual and narrative clashes which reflect the 'temples and trauma' trope embedded in Western imagination (Viet Lê 2021, 11-12). Where does he stand in all this? The artist leaves room for ambivalence.

Through the methodical, relentless, and meticulous deconstruction and reconstruction of overexposed cornerstones of Cambodia's past, he pursues a work of memorialization and engages the viewer to fill in the gaps. How can a country go from the Angkor Empire to the Khmer Rouge regime? What happened to Cambodia and its people? Whose story is being told and by whom? As variations of the same motif, the *Splendor and Darkness*, *Cambodia Reamker* and *Monuments and Memorial* series emphasize Lê's relentless desire to make sense of Cambodia's complex past.

His approach is reminiscent of mat weaving, a widespread yet dwindling handicraft in Cambodia and Vietnam. He learned the technique from his aunt as a child. Mat weaving consists of interlacing plain or dyed dried reed strips onto a simple horizontal loom set on the ground to create checkerboard, diamond, and stylized floral patterns. It commonly requires the work of two weavers. Through the use of images with opposite narratives, as well as black and white or monochrome prints, the artist explores a realm of visual and semantic oxymorons balancing between the personal and collective, past and present, vernacular and archival, and fictional and historical. Another textile that comes to mind is the end-on-end fabric, called "fil-à-fil" in French which literally

means “thread-to-thread.” This type of plain weave cloth presents heathered effects, stripes or small geometric motifs through the alternating of light and dark warp and weft threads. In the large *Splendor and Darkness* series produced in 2017, Dinh Q Lê emphasizes the materiality and making process engaged in his pieces by keeping fringes of uneven rows of warp strips at the bottom of #28, #29, #31, or by showing visibly frayed and burnt edges on the diamond-shaped #11 and #13 [Figs.3-4]. From large tapestry-like pieces [#32] to saturated cyanotype pieces as if they were dipped in indigo dye [#26; #27], textile visual and technical vocabulary underlies each artwork to develop a specific landscape of sensory emotions and connections.

Between textuality and tactility, new meanings are formed to overcome the silence and numbness imposed by trauma and enact a dynamic response. From witnesses, viewers become willing participants in this interpretive and memory work. In brief, through its compelling textility, Dinh Q Lê’s exhibition offers multitudes. His photo-weavings and installations activate unspoken, intangible and embodied meanings layered within, as crucial ways to memorialize, remember and acknowledge Cambodia and Vietnam’s violent histories and their lingering effects and legacies in the post-war period.

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Figures

Figure 1.

Figure 2.

Figure 3.

Figure 4.

Figure captions

Figure 1. Wall of black and white photographs of female prisoners at S21, Tuol Sleng Genocide Museum. Author's picture. Courtesy of Tuol Sleng Genocide Museum, 2022.

Figure 2. Video stills of Dinh Q Lê. Author's picture, 2022. Courtesy of Musée du quai Branly.

Figure 3. *Splendor and Darkness #28* (2017), cyanotype on Stonehenge paper; cut, woven and burnt, with acid-free double-sided tape and linen tape. Author's picture, 2022. Courtesy of Musée du quai Branly.

Figure 4. *Splendor and Darkness #13* (2017), Foiling and screen print on Stonehenge paper; woven and burnt, with acid-free double-sided tape and linen tape. Author's picture, 2022. Courtesy of Musée du quai Branly.